

FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE: SILKWORM PUPAE MEAL AS A SUSTAINABLE PROTEIN IN AQUACULTURE

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ABSTRACT

It is estimated that the consumption of animal products will increase by 60-70% in 2050. The rise in consumption will necessitate substantial resources, with feed presenting the greatest challenge due to the restricted availability, ongoing climate changes, and competition for food and fuel. The expenses of conventional feed components like fishmeal and soybean meal are also rather high, and their supply is anticipated to be limited. Raising insects might be a part of possible answers. Several investigations were undertaken to assess the utilization of insect meals as a component of particular animal species' diets. Silkworm pupae are frequently regarded as a viable substitute for fish meal because of their considerable nutritional advantages. Dry silkworm pupae contain 50-70% crude protein and 24-33% crude fat, making them an excellent source of insect protein with a balanced essential amino acid profile. The conducted review illustrates the antioxidant properties and significant levels of unsaturated fatty acids, which play a role in lowering the risk of specific cancer types and inflammatory responses. The research conducted on several fish species resulted in the development of suggested inclusion amounts of silkworm pupae meal in the diets of the specified aquaculture species. This study aims to emphasize the importance of silkworm pupae meal as a cost-effective protein alternative for the aquaculture sector in comparison to expensive traditional protein sources, as well as its influence on fish growth and physiological responses.

Keywords: *Silkworm pupae meal, protein source, fish meal, fish feed, soybean meal*

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture stands as the largest sector in food production, presenting significant opportunities to enhance sustainable food supply. Aquaculture produced 114.5 million metric tons of live weight in 2018, reflecting the ongoing growth of the sector (Bartley, 2022). Aquaculture is crucial for the preservation of food security by providing high-quality food to the world's growing population (Pradeepkiran, 2019). The aquaculture sector has shown an effective annual growth rate

of 2.1%, surpassing the growth rates of other animal production sectors such as livestock. The significant contributions of the aquaculture and fisheries sectors to the economy can be attributed to their roles in production, sales, and marketing (Azra et al., 2021; Cai & Leung, 2020). While aquaculture offers numerous benefits for food availability, its sustainability is contingent upon several factors, such as knowledge, experience, ecological conditions, and the existence of a

substantial market for aquaculture (Broitman et al., 2017). At present, half of the global fish production comes from aquaculture, highlighting its importance as a significant source of protein, in terms of both quantity and nutritional content (Tacon, 2020). Organisms from both land and water contribute approximately 43% of global protein sources and are crucial in combating malnutrition, particularly in developing countries. Aquaculture production, similar to other forms of terrestrial farming, relies entirely on the availability of nutrients for feed. Aquaculture is a relatively new industry in Pakistan, primarily practiced in extensive and semi-extensive freshwater systems. Although its effect on the national economy may be minimal, aquaculture represents a significant area of inquiry at certain times due to its potential to enhance the domestic supply of high-quality protein in Pakistan. Approximately 400,000 individuals are directly engaged in fishing, with an additional 600,000 working in associated sectors. The projected annual fish production stands at approximately 0.6 MMT, with 63% sourced from marine environments and 37% from inland sources. Pakistan hosts nearly 800 distinct species of saltwater fish and 193 species of freshwater fish. The existence of significant aquaculture industries depends on the necessity for aquatic feed, which is crucial for achieving high yields. It is noteworthy that feed constitutes over 60% of the total expenses in aquaculture, highlighting the significant impact that developing more affordable aquatic feeds could have on the remarkable expansion of this industry. Protein is a crucial component of a fish diet. In aquatic feed, the primary sources of protein include fish meal, scale meal, feather meal, bone meal, and blood meal (Daniel, 2018). Fish meal is essential to the development of the aquaculture sector. Because of its balanced amino acid profile, high protein content, and rapid digestion. FM is recognized as an important source of protein for aquaculture feed. Moreover, the superior quality of FM enhances fertility growth and improves the feed conversion ratio. Annual production of fish meal in Pakistan is estimated to be between 40,000 and 45,000 tonnes (Amman et al., 2020).

The rising demand for fish meal in aquaculture and poultry production is pushing prices higher and exacerbating the burden on already overfished oceans (Khan et al., 2013). Furthermore, it has been noted that the development rates of specific finfish species are hindered when their diets include elevated levels of protein derived from fish meal (Ahmad et al., 2020). The increasing cost of fish meal is expected to elevate manufacturing expenses, highlighting the need for the creation of alternative, more affordable protein sources.

Previous research suggested that plant-based diets might harm fish health and growth, maybe because of anti-nutritional elements (Molinari et al., 2020; Serra et al., 2021). Among plant-based diets, soybean emerges as the most effective alternative to fishmeal, due to its economic benefits and abundant nutritional content (Rawles et al., 2018). The examination of the nutritional content of soybean meal consists of 44% crude protein, 11% moisture, 24.7% lipids, and 31.85% carbs. Nonetheless, the inclusion of soybean meal in the fish diet has been shown to negatively impact growth, liver integrity, microbiota of the intestine, and the immune response in various fish species. The use of SBM-based diets for feeding salmonids led to notable gut health complications, marked by intestinal infection and increased inflammatory responses in the fish (Randazzo et al., 2021). One of the drawbacks of utilizing soybean meal in fish diets is that it is sourced from international suppliers, such as Argentina, Brazil, and the United States. Consequently, the cost is exceedingly high. The significant expense represents the foremost obstacle to achieving sustainability in Pakistan's aquaculture sector. It is essential to create novel aquafeeds that incorporate innovative feed ingredients capable of replacing soybean meal and mitigating the negative impacts linked to plant proteins (Gasco et al., 2018; López-Pedrouso et al., 2020).

Silkworm Pupae Meal

Sericulture began in China around the 27th century BC and subsequently disseminated to various regions worldwide. In 2011, global production of silkworm cocoons reached approximately 485,000 tons (Häbeanu et al.,

2024). Currently, India stands out as the leading nation in both the consumption and production of silk globally. India is known for four distinct varieties of silk: Mulberry, Tassar, Muga, and Eri. Among these, Mulberry silk, produced by the farmed silkworm (*Bombyx Mori*), stands out as the most popular. The major byproduct of the industry is 8 kg of pupae for every kilogram of silk made. About 60% of the weight of cocoons is consistently disposed of in the environment (Sathishkumar et al., 2021). The boiled cocoons of silkworm larvae are carefully ground and dried to create silkworm meal which contains 56% protein (Tomotake et al., 2010). In the Indo-Pacific regions, silkworm pupae have been utilized as a component of fish feed for an extended period. The prolonged incorporation of raw pupae results in the development of an off flavor and odor. Fish food can also be produced from deceased moths and SWP. Scientific studies indicate that de-oiled SWP meal serves as an exceptional fish food due to its higher protein content compared to regular SWP meal (Karthick Raja et al., 2019). In comparison to other animal by-products, SWPM exhibits a certain deficiency in minerals (3-10% DM); the incorporation of these minerals into fish diets leads to enhanced growth performance (Sheikh et al., 2018).

Environmental challenges of silkworm pupae disposal

After the process of reeling silk from the cocoons, the wasted silkworm pupae are usually abandoned in the region without adequate disposal measures. The fresh silkworm pupae are a product that decomposes rapidly, leading to environmental pollution and generating an unpleasant odor in the surroundings. Large volumes of pupae are disposed of in areas that produce silk, which

presents serious environmental problems (Yhoun-Aree et al., 1997). The environmental effect of the silk business may be considerably reduced by using these resources for manufacturing useful biological compounds like chitin, fatty acids, oil, and proteins, as well as for the nourishment of livestock and poultry.

Nutrient potential of silkworm pupae meal

Comprehensive research shows that SWPs have a balanced nutritional profile with essential sources of proteins, minerals, fats, and vitamins. In comparison to conventional food sources, these alternatives exhibit a greater concentration of three calorogenic nutrients providing up to 230 kcal per 100 g. The protein level of silkworm pupae is about 21.5%, which is higher than many traditional animal products. Reports indicated that the dry-weight protein content of silkworm pupae varies between 49% and 54% (Longvah et al., 2011; Nowak et al., 2016). Because silkworm pupae contain significant levels of necessary amino acids, their proteins are considered complete proteins. In general, insect proteins demonstrate a high degree of digestibility (Capinera & Finke, 2008) There is a noticeable amount of fat in edible insects. In particular, the fat content of dried silkworm pupae ranges from 25% to 30% (Kouřimská & Adámková, 2016). Silkworm pupae exhibit elevated levels of monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids while reduced quantity of saturated fat (Payne et al., 2016). Approximately 70% to 80% of the fatty acid composition in silkworm pupae consists of unsaturated fats (Zhao XingYu et al., 2015). One important source of useful fatty acids is silkworm pupae. Additionally, because tocopherol and phospholipids work effectively to prevent lipid oxidation (Kotake-Nara et al., 2002).

Table 1 Amino Acid Profile of Silkworm Pupae Expressed per 16 g Nitrogen

Amino acids	Non-defatted SWPM (g\16g Nitrogen)	Defatted SWPM (g\16g Nitrogen)
Essential Amino acids		
Leucine	7.5	5.8±0.2
Tryptophan	0.9	1.4±0.2
Methionine	3.5	3.0±0.4
lysine	7.0	6.1±0.4
Valine	5.5	4.9±0.2

Isoleucine	5.1	3.9±0.2
Phenylalanine	5.1	4.4±0.3
Histidine	2.6	2.6±0.1
Threonine	5.2	4.8±0.3
Non-essential amino acids		
Cysteine	1.0	0.8±0.5
Tyrosine	5.9	5.5±0.2
Alanine	5.8	4.4±0.2
Glycine	4.8	3.7±0.3
Aspartic acid	10.4	7.8±0.7
Proline	5.2	5.2±0.1
Glutamic acid	13.9	8.3±0.7
Serine	5.0	4.5±0.2
Arginine	5.6	5.1±0.3

Source: (Makkar et al., 2014).

Table 2 Dry Matter Proximate Composition of Silkworm Pupae Meal

Contents	Silkworm Meal	Reference
DM (%)	90.9	(Fagoonee, 1983)
CP (%)	68.7	(Panda, 1970)
Fat (%)	24.19	(Kowalska et al., 2020)
Ash (%)	2.10	(Lin et al., 1983)
NEF (%)	6.27	(Hossain et al., 1997)
Moisture (%)	10	(Panda, 1970)

Proximate composition values are expressed as percentages and are calculated on a dry matter basis (g/100 g dry weight). CP stands for Crude Protein, DM refers to Dry Matter, CF indicates Crude Fiber, EE denotes Ether Extract, and NEF means Nitrogen Free Extract.

Biological Activity Of Silkworm Pupae Meal Natural Antioxidants

Silkworm pupae meal is rich in natural antioxidants, rendering it a significant component in food products (Deori et al., 2014). Because of their ability to prevent oxidation and protect cells from damage, thiol and ascorbic acid have been used to achieve several research goals in the regulation of oxidative stress. According to recent research, silkworm pupae have a variety of applications, one of which is as a natural antioxidant (Anootherthato et al., 2019). The efficacy of the generated antioxidants may be influenced by the conditions of hydrolysis, including pH and temperature. 95% of the antioxidant reduction activity of silkworm pupae hydrolysates that were spray-dried and generated at pH 4–8 was

preserved, whereas over 30% was diminished in alkaline conditions (pH > 10) (Shi et al., 2018). Ghosh et al. (2020) observed that the antioxidant peptides, have greater scavenging abilities and may be useful as a natural antioxidant. Because of their antioxidant properties, specific peptides derived from silkworm pupae may thus be used to treat many medical conditions, enhancing their benefits.

Silkworm Pupae As A Source Of Antimicrobial Peptides

Since antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains have recently emerged, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), whether derived from nature or synthesized, have garnered a lot of attention as potential substitutes for traditional antibiotics. The silkworm provides an exciting prospect for the generation of recombinant AMPs. Recombinant production of cyto-insect-toxin utilizing the silkworm *B. mori* Bacmid system for Nuclear Polyhedrosis Virus (Ali et al., 2014). The study employs recombinant proteins and induces expression patterns to examine the functional divergence of

antimicrobial peptides in silkworm pupae. The findings demonstrated significant antimicrobial capabilities that could successfully eradicate infections caused by microbiomes (Yang et al., 2011). The pupae of *Hyalophora cecropia* and *S. ricini*, two enormous silk moths, have remarkable antibacterial peptides and characteristics (Yi et al., 2014). Furthermore, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* were inhibited by the hot press separation of extracts from silkworm pupae (Saviane et al., 2021). Silkworm pupae-derived polypeptides can selectively prevent the growth of particular cancerous cells and the division of spleen cells (Jeong et al., 2017). Silkworm pupae's antibacterial composition offers a viable option for drug development.

Impact Of Silkworm Based Diet In Jian Carp

The first genetically modified new kind of common carp available in China is Jian carp (Zhou et al., 2008). It shows far greater growth than ordinary carp and has more protein and essential amino acids. The effect of substituting silkworm pupae meal for varying quantities of dietary fish meal (0, 50%, 60%, 70%, and 80%) on juvenile Jian carp was examined in this study. Groups of eighteen fish were fed one of five isonitrogenous diets (SP0, SP50, SP60, SP70, or SP80) for 8 weeks. The fish in the SP60, SP70, and SP80 groups had significantly lower body weights as well as specific growth rates than the SP0 group. The muscle protein level of the SP50 group was considerably higher than that of the SP80 group ($P \leq 0.05$). In all groups, there was an increase in malondialdehyde (MDA) content, with the SP80 group exhibiting the most significant difference. Conversely, hepatic superoxide dismutase activity decreased as FM levels rose. The gene expression level of heat shock protein 70 in the SP70 group showed a significant increase compared to the SP0 group ($P \leq 0.05$). In contrast, the expression in the SP80 group was significantly reduced compared to that in the SP70 group ($P \leq 0.05$). The SP80 group showed significant reductions in intestinal protease activity, increased ALT and AST levels, irregular hepatocytes, and changes in the villi of the intestine. The data show that substituting 50 percent of the FM with soybean meal in Jian carp

diet is viable; however, larger doses of soybean protein are not recommended (Zhang JianLu et al., 2013)

Impact Of Silkworm Based Diet In Nile Tilapia

This study examined the impact of incorporating silkworm meals and bioprocessed silkworm meals as an alternative to fish meals on the growth performance of GIFT tilapia over a growth trial of 60 days conducted in floating cages. The protein in the fish meal was substituted with 0, 333.3, 666.7, and 1000 g/kg of SWP and BSWP, respectively, to provide seven experimental meals that were isonitrogenous, iso-lipidic, and isoenergetic. The diets were categorized as control, SWP 33.33, SWP 66.67, SWP 100, BSWP 33.33, BSWP 66.67, and BSWP 100. Three groups of thirty tilapia juveniles, each with an initial average weight of 11.34 ± 0.16 g, were given experimental diets three times daily until they displayed signs of satisfaction. The increase in weight was significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) in the SWP 66.67, BSWP 66.67, and BSWP 100 dietary groups. Furthermore, BSWP at 66.67 had a considerably ($p \leq 0.05$) greater FCR and SGR. The addition of SWP and BSWP to the feed of GIFT tilapia did not significantly alter their overall chemical and amino acid composition or their haemato-biochemical responses. The results show that in the diets of GIFT tilapia, both SWP and BSWP can completely replace dietary fish meal. However, the bioprocessed SWP at 666.7 g/kg exhibited the most advantageous growth performance (Sathishkumar et al., 2021).

Impact Of Silkworm Based Diet In Pacific White Shrimp

The study investigated the effects of substitution of FM with soybean meal (SBM) and silkworm meal on growth, survival rate, and feed efficiency of juvenile white leg shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei* throughout a 60-day feeding trial. Five experimental diets that were iso-nitrogenous and included 35% protein each were made. In the four experimental diets, soybean meal and silkworm pupae meal were substituted for fishmeal (FM) at different inclusion levels: 25% (Diet 2: 25% SBM + SPM), 50% (Diet 3: 50% SBM + SPM), 75% (Diet 4: 75% SBM + SPM), and 100% (Diet 5:

100% SBM + SPM). The control diet was made up of only FM (Diet 1). Shrimp were divided into quadruplicate groups of ten individuals per aquarium and given a daily feed amount equal to 10% of their body weight. These groups were then randomly assigned to five distinct experimental diets. To evaluate growth performance and adjust the ratio appropriately, sampling was done at 15-day intervals. Following a 60-day feeding study, shrimp that were administered Diet 3 exhibited notable differences in WG, SGR, FCR, FER, and PER when compared to the other dietary groups. All experimental diets demonstrated a complete survival rate of 100%. Additionally, compared to shrimp in the other diet groups, those fed the feed that replaced 50% of the fishmeal with soybean meal and shrimp protein meal (Diet 3) showed a noticeably increased crude protein content in their carcass. Nonetheless, there was a notable reduction in moisture and ash content as the proportion of fishmeal substitution increased from 0% to 100%. The findings of this investigation demonstrate that replacing 50% of the fishmeal protein in the diets of juvenile *Litopenaeus vannamei* with soybean meal and silkworm pupae meal is viable, while maintaining the shrimp's body composition, growth performance, and feed intake (Hodar & Sushila, 2022).

Impact of silkworm based diet in Rainbow trout

Over the course of a 60-day experimental period, the study investigated the effects on rainbow trout growth, survival, and body composition by using varying amounts of silkworm pupae as a substitute for fish meal, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. A total of 360 fingerlings, were randomly assigned to four treatment groups. The treatment groups consisted of three replicates, each with thirty fish. T1 was assigned 52.5% FM; T2 was allocated 5% SP along with 47.5% FM; T3 was given 10% SP combined with 42.5% FM; and T4 was provided with 15% SP and 37.5% FM. A single group was designated as the control. At the end of the experiment, the results showed that 10% of FM could be replaced with SP without negatively affecting the feed conversion ratio, survival growth rate, weight gain, thermal condition factor, protein content, lipid content when using soybean

meal and silkworm pupae meal (Shakoori et al., 2016).

Impact of silkworm-based diet on Rainbow shark

The investigation focused on evaluating the effects of substituting fishmeal with silkworm pupae meal on the growth and maturation of Rainbow sharks (*Epalzeorhynchus frenatum*). Four experimental diets were formulated incorporating silkworm pupae (SWP) as a substitute for fish meal at 3 different levels: 30% (T1), 40% (T2), and 50% (T3), alongside a control diet that contained only fish meal. The experimental trial was carried out in hapas, in duplicate, set up in an earthen pond. The fish were introduced at a density of 10 individuals per hapa. Throughout the experimental phase, special care was given to monitoring water quality parameters. T1, T2, and T3 designated as experimental diets demonstrated a significant enhancement in growth performance relative to the control diet C. The analysis of the four diets revealed that T1 exhibited a significantly higher weight gain, specific growth rate, protein efficiency ratio, and feed conversion ratio of 1.91 ± 0.06 in comparison to the other treatment groups. The fish acquiring diet T1 demonstrated the highest gonadosomatic index, GSI, at 14.90% compared to all other diets evaluated. The fish that were provided with the experimental diets exhibited comparable stages of maturity by the conclusion of the trial, especially noted in the late vitellogenin phase. The results of this investigation demonstrate that SWP has the potential to act as a cost-effective source of animal protein, successfully replacing fish meal by as much as 30% in dietary formulations (Raja et al., 2020).

Impact of silkworm-based diet on catfish

This investigation entailed a ninety-day feeding trial on fingerlings of striped catfish (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* S.). The study aimed to assess the impact of partially substituting conventional protein sources with non-deoiled silkworm pupae meal across various parameters, such as growth performance, protein utilization, metabolic enzymes, haemato-biochemical profiles, non-specific immune responses, stress enzymes,

and hepato-histopathology. Five extruded floating diets were created with varying proportions of pupae meal as a substitute for fishmeal: 0% (NDSWP0), 25% (NDSWP25), 50% (NDSWP50), 75% (NDSWP75), and 100%. The NDSWP0 diet served as the control group. The study indicated that striped catfish fed with NDSWP50, NDSWP75, and NDSWP100 showed significantly lower biomass, percentage weight gain, feed conversion ratio, and protein efficiency ratio when compared to the NDSWP25 diet group. Additionally, apart from NDSWP25, the other dietary treatments showed a significant decrease in the hepatosomatic index ($P \geq 0.05$). The activity of alkaline phosphatase, an enzyme involved in liver metabolism, significantly declined. No notable variations in the non-specific immune parameters, particularly respiratory burst activity and lysozyme, were detected across the dietary groups ($P \leq 0.05$). The serum SOD activity exhibited an increase from NDSWP0 to NDSWP50. The treatment groups showed significantly lower levels of blood hemoglobin and hematocrit, as well as serum total protein, albumin, globulin, and triglyceride content ($P \leq 0.05$). Additionally, the hepato-histopathological examination demonstrated the infiltration of leukocytes characterized by eosinophilic granular cell intensification, along with hepatocyte vacuolization at the periphery and loosely arranged polyhedral hepatocytes as the replacement level escalates. In summary, full-fat non-mulberry silkworm pupae meal serves as an appropriate dietary feedstuff that can replace fishmeal at 25%, without negatively impacting the overall health status of striped catfish fingerlings (Das et al.)

Conclusion

Insect meals present a promising alternative for partially or fully substituting fish meal, primarily because of the adaptability and capacity of insects to modify their amino acid and fatty acid compositions. Furthermore, insects serve as essential nutritional resources for fish, particularly those found in continental habitats. This study highlights the SWP as a significant source of proteins, lipids, and minerals, establishing it as a viable alternative dietary supplement for fish feed.

Due to its lower cost and distinct composition, SWP serves as an excellent alternative to fish meal. This allows production costs to be lowered with no effect on the growth performance of fish raised for food. Furthermore, environmental pollution can be reduced through appropriate processing and effective use of valuable resources.

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Author contributions

AT has done writing review and editing, FI has helped in writing, SU has done editing, HJ helped in writing, and HS has done writing, NM has performed review, editing, and conceptualization, RM helped in reviewing.

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